

KEY PLAN

CDM RESIDUAL RISKS

THIS DRAWING HAS BEEN REVIEWED AGAINST THE DESIGN CDM ROLLING RISK REGISTER AND KNOWN SIGNIFICANT RESIDUAL RISKS HAVE BEEN IDENTIFIED.

CONSTRUCTION	 SIGNIFICANT HAZARD REF.
MAINTENANCE/CLEANING	
DECOMMISSIONING/DEMOLITION	

NOTES

GF REF. IMAGE FLOORING
GROUND FLOOR PLAN

GF REF. IMAGE RACK ARCH
GROUND FLOOR PLAN

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name	SANIA MASKATIYA	
project	HOUSE OF ITTEHAD	
drawing	REF. IMAGES	
computer file	plot date	02-17-24
project number	scale	
drawing number	rev	issue status
INT-01	00	

This drawing is to be read in conjunction with all related drawings. Do not scale from this drawing. All dimensions must be checked and verified on site before commencing any work or producing shop drawings. The originator should be notified immediately of any discrepancy. This drawing is copyright and remains the property of ARRIS Consultants.

GF

REF. IMAGE FLOOR HANGING ROD
GROUND FLOOR PLAN

GF

REF. IMAGE CEILING/WALL PANELLING
GROUND FLOOR PLAN

KEY PLAN

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CONSTRUCTION	
MAINTENANCE/CLEANING	
DECOMMISSIONING/DEMOLITION	

NOTES

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name
SANIA MASKATIYA

project
HOUSE OF ITTEHAD

drawing
REF. IMAGES

computer file	plot date	02-17-24
project number	scale	

drawing number	rev	issue status
INT-02	00	

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GF REF. IMAGE TRY ROOM STOOL
GROUND FLOOR PLAN

GF REF. IMAGE TRY ROOM INTERIOR
GROUND FLOOR PLAN

GF REF. IMAGE COUNTER/WALL PANELLING
GROUND FLOOR PLAN

KEY PLAN

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CONSTRUCTION	SIGNIFICANT HAZARD REF
MAINTENANCE/CLEANING	
DECOMMISSIONING/DEMOLITION	

NOTES

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name
SANIA MASKATIYA

project
HOUSE OF ITTEHAD

drawing
REF. IMAGES

computer file
plot date
02-17-24

project number
scale

drawing number
INT-02
rev
00
issue status

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DECOMMISSIONING/DEMOLITION	

NOTES

EXISTING LAYOUT

GF

GROUND FLOOR PLAN

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name	SANIA MASKATIYA
project	HOUSE OF ITTEHAD

drawing	EXISTING LAYOUT GROUND FLOOR PLAN	
computer file	plot date	02-17-24
project number	scale	
drawing number	rev	issue status
INT-03	00	

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KEY PLAN

DEMOLISHING LEGENDS

— DEMOLISHED WALL

— DEMOLISHED GLASS

DEMOLISH PLAN
GF
GROUND FLOOR PLAN

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CONSTRUCTION	SIGNIFICANT HAZARD REF
MAINTENANCE/CLEANING	
DECOMMISSIONING/DEMOLITION	

NOTES

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name	SANIA MASKATIYA	
project	HOUSE OF ITTEHAD	
drawing	ADD/DEMOLISH PLAN GROUND FLOOR PLAN	
computer file	plot date	02-17-24
project number	scale	
drawing number	rev	issue status
INT-04	00	

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DECOMMISSIONING/DEMOLITION	

NOTES

FURNITURE LAYOUT
GROUND FLOOR PLAN

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name
SANIA MASKATIYA

project
HOUSE OF ITTEHAD

drawing
PROPOSED LAYOUT
GROUND FLOOR PLAN

computer file	plot date	02-17-24
project number	scale	

drawing number	rev	issue status
INT-05	00	

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MAINTENANCE/CLEANING	
DECOMMISSIONING/DEMOLITION	

NOTES

GF FLOORING LAYOUT
GROUND FLOOR PLAN

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name	SANIA MASKATIYA	
project	HOUSE OF ITTEHAD	
drawing	FLOORING LAYOUT GROUND FLOOR PLAN	
computer file	plot date	02-17-24
project number	scale	
drawing number	rev	issue status
INT-07	00	

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DECOMMISSIONING/DEMOLITION	

NOTES

G.F. ELEVATION - 01
GROUND FLOOR

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name	SANIA MASKATIYA
project	HOUSE OF ITTEHAD

drawing
ELEVATION-01
GROUND FLOOR PLAN

computer file	plot date	02-17-24
project number	scale	

drawing number	rev	issue status
INT-09	00	

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MAINTENANCE/CLEANING	
DECOMMISSIONING/DEMOLITION	

NOTES

G.F. ELEVATION - 02
GROUND FLOOR

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name	SANIA MASKATIYA
project	HOUSE OF ITTEHAD

drawing	ELEVATION-02 GROUND FLOOR PLAN
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computer file	plot date	02-17-24
project number	scale	
drawing number	rev	issue status
INT-10	00	

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MAINTENANCE/CLEANING	
DECOMMISSIONING/DEMOLITION	

NOTES

G-F FLOOR HANGING

G-F FLOOR HANGING

GF REF. IMAGE FLOOR HANGING ROD
GROUND FLOOR PLAN

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name	SANIA MASKATIYA
project	HOUSE OF ITTEHAD

drawing	FLOOR HANGING ROD DETAIL GROUND FLOOR PLAN
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computer file	plot date	02-17-24
project number	scale	
drawing number	rev	issue status
INT-12	00	

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NOTES

G-F LAYOUT PLAN TRY ROOM

G-F ELEVATION-01 TRY ROOM

G-F ELEVATION-02 TRY ROOM

G-F ELEVATION-03 TRY ROOM

G-F ELEVATION-04 TRY ROOM

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name
SANIA MASKATIYA

project
HOUSE OF ITTEHAD

drawing
TRY ROOM DETAIL
GROUND FLOOR PLAN

computer file
plot date
02-17-24

project number
scale

drawing number
INT-14

rev
00

issue status

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